

Regional Impact Analysis of Large-scale Research Infrastructures

ADDENDUM FCC-GOV-CC-0185 (KE4819/ATS)

Case study selection and methodology

(LSE-RD-1.2-1.3/Doc)

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The FCCIS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant No 951754

The London School of Economics (LSE) has received funding from European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) under Addendum FCC-GOV-CC-0185 (KE4819/ATS), defining LSE contribution under Article 6 of the Memorandum of Understanding for the Future Circular Collider Innovation Study (FCCIS) (FCC-GOV-CC-0004, EDMS 1390795) hosted by CERN.

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Executive summary

This report has been prepared as part of the regional impact of Large-scale research infrastructures (RIs) study agreed between the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) and the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE) (deliverables LSE-RD 1.2 and 1.3 - Regional impact analysis Project). Building on the inception report (LSE-RD 1.1) that identified procurement as the primary channel through which RIs can affect local economic performance, this document has four main objectives:

- To outline the criteria for the selection of the case study, in terms of project, technology and region, for the regional impact analysis on RI procurement;
- To propose a framework and methodological approach through which these regional benefits can be identified and estimated;
- To identify the most appropriate case study for the analysis;
- To set out the plan for the completion of the project and identify potential challenges.

This report identifies superconducting radiofrequency (SRF) cavities as the technology to focus on for this regional analysis. To estimate the potential impact of this technology, this document proposes to analyze the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) facility in Germany, the largest deployment of SRF technology to date. More specifically, after examining the two SRF cavities suppliers for the XFEL project and mapping out this technology's production and procurement process, this document identifies E. Zanon¹ and the municipality of Schio (Italy), where this company is located, as the focus for the study.

After considering the case study's specificities, this report identifies the synthetic control method (SCM) as the most appropriate counterfactual technique for this analysis. This is the first time that state-of-the-art counterfactual methods are used to estimate the local socio-economic impact of RIs. Its main advantage is that it can be replicated in other settings to test the external validity of the findings of this study.

This paper also sets out the next steps for completing the project, focusing on the production of impact estimates using the SCM analysis.

¹ In 2020, the physics business branch of E. Zanon was acquired by SIMIC and a new company, Zanon Research & Innovation SRL, was created.

Section 1: Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Large Research Infrastructures (RIs) are crucial for advancing science for two reasons. Firstly, science evolves rapidly and to push forward the frontiers of scientific knowledge, scientists need new experimental instruments. Secondly, new scientific discoveries are increasingly becoming the result of collaborative efforts. RIs involve a wide range of actors such as universities and other research centres, receive funds from national governments and work with several industrial partners to develop new cutting-edge technologies needed to fulfil their ambitious research objectives (Bastianin et al., 2021). Because of all these features, RIs can play an important role in the creation of innovation systems.

Understanding the socio-economic impact of RI at different levels (local, regional, national, global) is crucial for both RIs managers and policymakers. Governments want answers to the following questions: given finite amounts of annual budgets, which RIs should a government fund over long periods? Are there benefits for society of supporting these projects that go beyond the long-term scientific gains? If positive effects can be identified, how widespread are they, and who benefits from them?

While it is important to identify the socio-economic returns of these scientific endeavours, incorporating socio-economic aspects into RI planning and design poses some critical challenges and questions for the scientific community. For example, to what extent and how can an infrastructure pursue societally beneficial goals that are separate from its main scientific missions without negatively affecting these?

1.2 Existing evidence and gaps

In recent years, this debate has led to the development of new methods to evaluate the socio-economic impact of RIs. Most of the literature has focused on the effects of procurement, and this is because the quest for new discoveries needs ever more complex components. Consequently, technology-intensive equipment takes an increasingly higher share of the budget for these scientific projects and involves more specialized firms. The significant funds involved, the technology intensity of these contracts and the required collaboration between industry and scientists to design and develop these products have

made procurement a likely and identifiable channel through which spillovers can occur. At the same time, procurement has become an important tool for innovation policy - public procurement for innovation (PPI) - having the potential to support the development of novel technologies that are too risky for the private sector to invest in (Uyarra et al., 2014).

Much of the recent evidence on the effects of RI procurement comes from CERN, which hosts the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), one of the largest RIs ever built (Florio, 2019). Looking at LHC suppliers, Castelnovo et al. (2018) demonstrated that companies generally experienced a rise in R&D, patents, productivity, and profits after becoming CERN industrial partners. Florio et al. (2018) showed that CERN procurement significantly affects suppliers' innovative performance when a relational type of governance is in place through cooperative relations (i.e. exchanges implying that CERN and suppliers work closely to deal with complex information that is not easily transmitted or learned). Bastianin et al. (2021) showed that collaborating with CERN is associated with an increase in the hazard to file a patent for the first time and in the number of patent applications. Studies also found that spillovers to second-tier suppliers impact the entire supply chain (Florio et al., 2018). However, most of the latest socio-economic studies measure the effects to direct beneficiaries of procurement contracts. The benefits are likely to go beyond the boundaries of individual firms and affect the entire local economy in which these firms are located and operate. But we still have no clear evidence on whether this is the case, the size of these potential effects and how widely they spread.

Beyond the size and type of contract, the magnitude and spatial distribution of these socio-economic effects are likely to depend on three other features of the procurement: the potential use of the technology outside scientific research, the specificities of the procurement and manufacturing processes, the demand for the technology within scientific research. Firm characteristics and local factors external to the firm may also play an important mediating role.

1.3 Aims

Against this background, this regional impact study attempts to fill this evidence gap. This document outlines the criteria for the case study selection and the methodology we propose to measure the local economic impact of RI procurement contracts. More specifically, this study focuses on a particular type of regional impact of RIs involved in High-Energy Physics (HEP).

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first quantitative study to use cutting-edge causal inference techniques to estimate the regional impact of RI procurement. More specifically, we use the synthetic control method (SCM) to estimate the causal effect of the contracts on the local economy in which the supplier is based.

To test our novel approach, together with CERN, we have decided to focus on one particular technology: superconducting radiofrequency (SRF) cavities. Two reasons justify this choice. Firstly, the SRF system will be at the heart of the FCC-ee (Benedikt, 2020). Secondly, SRF cavities are exclusively produced for particle accelerators, making it easier to attribute the impact that we observe to the procurement contract.

1.4 Challenges

When trying to estimate the effect of this technology, we face two challenges. Firstly, although this technology has existed for several decades, it was used in relatively small amounts in circular accelerators at CERN, including its flagship machine, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The reason is that circular particle accelerators do only need to accelerate particles in a single (or a few) places. Particles gain energy each time they pass this acceleration point as they orbit the machine. This makes this type of particle accelerator particularly flexible and energy-efficient. This means, however, that we cannot draw on CERN's recent evidence to understand the potential impact of this particular technology. Secondly, we have to leverage the findings on the effect of this technology to forecast the potential regional impact of future investment.

To overcome the first challenge, after examining previous scientific projects involving the production of SRF cavities in industry, we have decided to focus on the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) facility in Germany. This is a linear particle accelerator

composed of many radiofrequency systems, and it is the largest deployment of this technology to date. Two firms, E. Zanon (today Zanon Research & Innovation) and Research Instruments GmbH, located in two different countries, Italy and Germany, were involved in the XFEL production. In this study, we focus on E. Zanon and the municipality of Schio (Italy), where the company is located. Two factors have determined this choice. Firstly, the physics branch of E. Zanon has only one site. Secondly, the entire staff was involved in fulfilling the XFEL contract. This makes it easier to attribute the effect we might observe to the procurement contract and an ideal setting to test our methodology.

When it comes to the second challenge, while the methodology we propose guarantees internal validity (the link between cause and effect), we need to apply the same approach to different settings to improve external validity (the extent to which we can generalize these findings). Therefore, this study is a pilot. The resulting estimates need to be corroborated by applying the proposed methodology and framework to estimate the effects of different types of contracts involving other regions and firms as their features might mediate the impact.

1.5 Structure of the report

The rest of the report is structured as follows:

- Section 2 summarises the findings of our scoping study. In particular, it reports the insights from the expert interviews we conducted with firms and research institutes, and it justifies the case study selection;
- Section 3 outlines our approach to estimating the local impact: it describes the Synthetic control method and the potential application for this analysis;
- Section 4 concludes, highlighting this project's criticalities and outlining the timeframe for the rest of the study.

Section 2: Scoping study

This section outlines the choice of the Schio area in Italy for the investigations, where E. Zanon, one of the two companies that produced SRF cavities for the EXFEL project, is located. This choice was informed by a detailed analysis of related conference proceedings and by a series of expert interviews conducted between December 2020 and September 2021. The "pyramiding" sampling procedure (a variant of "snowballing") was used to build our sample of experts. This is a sampling method in which one interviewee provides the researcher with the name of one or more other potential interviewees more expert than themselves (Noy, 2008). Table 2 in the Appendix provides the complete list of interviewees.

The rest of this section starts by outlining the criteria for choosing SRF cavities as the technology for the case study. Secondly, it discusses the rationale for selecting the EXFEL project. Finally, it explains the reasons for selecting E. Zanon and, consequently, the area of Schio (Italy) as a pilot to test our novel approach.

2.1 SRF cavities

To estimate the regional effects that a particle-collider-based research infrastructure set up as a worldwide collaborative project can create, together with CERN, we have decided to focus on one particular technology, SRF cavities. Box 1 provides more details of SRF cavities and their market.

This technology met the following four criteria. Firstly, it is a technology that will be important for the FCC. The proposed FCC programme features as a first stage an electron-positron Higgs and electroweak factory (FCC-ee). SRF cavities will be at the heart of the FCC-ee: over 11 years, 341 cryomodules (containing 1364 cavities) will be produced (Benedikt, 2020). This would be the largest deployment of this technology to date.

Secondly, the selected technology should only be used in HEP so that we can attribute the effects we observe to the procurement contract. The interviews confirmed that SRF cavities, the only element of interest in this pilot study, are only used for particle accelerators. This does not exclude significant socio-economic impacts along the SRF value chain. For instance, advanced thin-film coating and forming methods for 3D complicated geometries have already been shown to be relevant for numerous consumer product areas.

Thirdly, the production of this technology needed close collaboration between RIs and firms. The evidence shows that this type of relationship is conducive to knowledge flows (Florio et al., 2018). This increases the possibility of knowledge spillovers that might benefit economic agents located in the supplier's area. Interviews with firms and RIs involved in the production of SRF cavities revealed that this type of collaboration was in place for most SRF cavities projects, particularly for the EXFEL project.

Fourthly, we wanted to select a technology that, beyond the primary element produced for a particle collider (the superconducting cavities), has potential for use outside HEP. This would increase the possibility of affecting the local economy. At the same time, to identify the effect of the contract, we wanted to focus on a technology that has not yet had an application outside the research domain. Although SRF cavities are only used in particle accelerators, a recent study showed that High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering, a coating technology that is being considered for the production of SRF cavities for FCC-ee to reduce its costs and increase quality, is already employed in some areas of automotive (e.g. reflectors), medical (e.g. implants) and communication industries (e.g. the coating of the Apple iPhone screen). CERN investment and demand could trigger new developments for this coating technology (Quach et al., 2021). Qualified personnel who can master this technology reliably are scarce and much sought after.

It is important to stress that other regional evaluations could have different criteria for selecting the technology and put less emphasis on the criteria listed here. In addition, SRF cavities are not necessarily the only technology to potentially generate regional economic impacts.

Box 1: SRF cavities market

The heart of a superconducting particle acceleration structure is a hollow structure called cavity, made of a superconducting material (or copper, coated with a superconducting material), in most cases niobium, chilled to near absolute zero with liquid helium. The generator fills the cavity with a radio-frequency electric field to accelerate the charged particles. These superconducting cavities conduct electric current with very small loss of energy so that a large amount of the energy coming from the electrical supply can be almost entirely transferred to the beam. The design of SRF varies depending on the particle types and energy requirements. Multiple SRF cavities are incorporated into linear assemblies known as cryomodules.

Superconducting radiofrequency systems technology has existed for 50 years (Peiniger et al., 2012). The first 20 years involved R&D and prototyping at research centres and universities. Industry has now been involved for 30 years in the production of cavities and accelerator modules with quality improvements over this period (Peiniger et al., 2012). The production of SRF cavities requires advanced milling and turning machines, metal forming, electron beam welding, and chemical treatment facilities (Peiniger et al., 2012), advanced thin-film production processes (e.g. magnetron sputtering) as well as novel forming processes such as electro-hydraulic forming. When the production of SRF cavities in the industry started, some machines could be found in companies involved in the manufacture of nuclear power plants. For companies not already having this equipment, a significant investment is required. The demand for SRF technologies has been stable through the last three decades and an average 100 cavities per year have been produced since the mid-1980s. However, interviews with the two companies revealed that demand fluctuates considerably. Research Instrument GmbH in Germany is the largest market player, producing on average 70 cavities per year since 2010. E. Zanon (now Zanon Research & Innovation) is the other company able to produce SRF cavities. The average value of one cavity built from bulk niobium is estimated at 100'000 euros in 2020 and this would suggest that the turnover for SRF cavity production is about 10 million euros (Peiniger et al., 2012). This is low if we take into consideration the initial investment to produce the cavities and it might explain the low number of firms involved in the production of SRF technology and why companies involved try to diversify. However, the cavity is only one small part of the SRF system and the turnover for the entire production is considerably higher.

In the last decade, the SRF market has been dominated by the construction of the European XFEL (840 cavities), the FRIB project at MSU (340 cavities) the ESS project at Lund (240 cavities) and SLAC (210 cavities) (Peiniger et al., 2012; Weise, 2014). Before EXFEL, only the fabrication was done by industry with the final treatment being done by the commissioning research institutes (Peiniger et al., 2012). EXFEL is the largest deployment of this technology project to date and included many partner laboratories and technology transfer to industry for mass production. If the ILC and the FCC-ee are built, the production of SRF cavities is set to increase in the coming years.

2.2 The EXFEL project

One of the challenges in measuring the potential regional impact of SRF cavities is that it has not been used at CERN in the scales and level of industry involvement needed for the FCC-ee. This means that one cannot use recent CERN procurement data and evidence to estimate the impact of this technology.

To address this challenge, we have examined past completed projects that have developed SRF systems with industry on a large scale. After having conducted interviews with staff at various research organizations (Jefferson Lab (United States), DESY (Germany), CERN (Switzerland), INFN (Italy)) and companies (Research Instruments (Germany), Zanon Research & Innovation (Italy), AES (USA), Roark (USA)), we have identified the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (EXFEL) in Germany as the primary case study for this analysis. Box 2 below provides more details on this project.

We have selected this case for two reasons. Firstly, this was the first project in which SRF cavities were mainly produced by industry. Before this production, only the mechanical fabrication was done by companies, while the surface treatment, the most demanding part of the production, was done by the commissioning research institutes (Singer et al., 2016). Secondly, this was the largest deployment of SRF cavities to date (Singer et al., 2016). And the underlying TESLA technology for these cavities has become the standard for other accelerators.

It is important to note that the methodological approach we outline in the next section could also be applied to other scientific projects that have adopted this technology in different quantities and qualities and various levels of industry involvement.

Box 2: The European XFEL

The European X-ray free-Electronic Laser (EXFEL) is a research facility located in the Hamburg area, Germany, where scientists from all over the world carry out experiments using X-ray flashes. The almost 2.1-km-long superconducting linear accelerator of the EXFEL will accelerate electrons to a maximum energy of 17.5 GeV by using a total of 808 SRF cavities installed in the three main linac sections.

To construct and operate the European XFEL, international partners created an independent research organisation – the European XFEL GmbH, a non-profit limited liability company under German law. The company employs more than 300 people. Twelve countries participated in this project: Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK. Its construction was a joint effort of its partners. It started in early 2009, with the first experiments beginning in September 2017. The costs amount to 1.25 billion euro (in 2005 prices). Germany covered 57% of these costs, Russia 26% and international partners the rest. Most of the contributions were in-kind.

2.3 The procurement and manufacturing process for EXFEL

Before discussing the criteria for the municipality selection, it is helpful to outline the specificities of procurement and production process of the SRF cavities for EXFEL as these might influence the magnitude of the territorial impact.

After a period of pre-qualification during which at least three companies were surveyed, the order for 840 cavities was placed in 2010. The production started in 2012 and ended in 2015. The first of the series cavities were delivered at the beginning of 2013. The National Centre Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) in Germany managed and assigned the contracts to two companies: Research Instruments GmbH in Bergisch Gladbach and Dortmund (Germany) and E. Zanon in Schio (Italy). E. Zanon and another company located in Schio – CSC Spa - also produced the helium tanks for this project.

Both companies were contracted to produce the same type of cavities, with each company responsible for producing half of the total number. The only difference was the choice for the final surface treatment step. Research Instruments GmbH used electrochemical polishing, whereas E. Zanon chose buffered chemical polishing for this last step.

The production was shared for two reasons. Firstly, companies wanted to develop their own expertise and infrastructure for the entire production process. Secondly, having two independent production facilities minimized the effects of potential disruptions in the production process. The production supervision was also shared: Milan's Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN) branch supervised E. Zanon, whereas DESY oversaw the production at Research Instrument GmbH.

Two options were considered for these contracts: "build to print" and "performance guarantee" (Singer et al., 2016). As this was the first time these firms were responsible for the entire production of SRF cavities, the selected suppliers added a significant premium to the second option. To reduce the costs, DESY decided to go for the "build to print" contract. Although the companies did not disclose the agreement's details, the selling price for each SRF cavity for other projects was approximately 100' 000 euros. This suggests that each contract was worth around 40 million euros².

The industrial production of SRF cavities required broad knowledge transfer from both DESY and INFN to the two suppliers. As part of the contract with DESY, the infrastructure at both companies was upgraded to meet the necessary requirements for the surface treatment of the cavities. The two companies were advised by the two research organizations on purchasing the new machinery and received training on how to use the latest equipment. Some of the new infrastructures included: new ISO4 and ISO7 cleanrooms, slow pumping/cold venting vacuum units, ethanol rinsing facility, a wash system for bringing cavities into the cleanroom, a new high-vacuum oven for 800 degrees Celsius annealing of niobium cavities (Singer et al. 2016). The contracts also required that both companies had a few specialized roles, such as a physicist, a chemist and a material scientist, and E. Zanon had to hire new staff to fulfil this specific requirement.

Staff at the two firms and the RIs involved defined the EXFEL project as a "game-changer": due to the costly infrastructure upgrade and training received, the gap between these two companies and other competitors had increased, giving them a competitive advantage when bidding for new contracts. Both companies received other SRF cavities contracts after EXFEL.

² Interviews with the two companies revealed that, given the large quantity of cavities, a small discount was applied.

Looking at the features of the agreement, the "build to print" contract meant that the production of the cavities had to meet the strict EXFEL specifications. To meet the stringent requirements, a comprehensive production monitoring system was implemented.

The central monitoring actions consisted of work according to a well-defined Quality Control (QC) Plan, internal Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Management system, and monthly progress reports (Singer et al., 2016). In addition, a project meeting took place at the company sites (on average once per month), with visits to the companies by the DESY and INFN SRF cavities experts. On top of this, the two research institutes carried out an additional QC. Figure 1 illustrates the various steps we have just described.

Figure 1: Overview of procurement and production processes for XFEL

Source: Based on information from [Pagani \(2012\)](#), [Singer et al. \(2013\)](#), and input with INFN and DESY staff.

Overall, this indicates constant knowledge flows between the different organizations. Although both firms mentioned that HEP was not the most profitable business, they confirmed that the expertise acquired during this partnership was valuable for further contracts. The two companies also valued the new contacts acquired due to this collaboration.

When looking at the manufacturing process, conference proceedings and interviews revealed that the production almost entirely happened within the boundaries of the two firms with little involvement of subcontractors. DESY sourced the high purity niobium and shipped it to the two manufacturers (Singer et al., 2016). Looking at the different production steps, only the low-added initial production phases - part of the deep drawing from the niobium

sheets - were outsourced to other local Italian and German firms. Figure 2 illustrates these different production steps. Overall, the low involvement of subcontractors suggests that most of the direct benefits accrued to the two firms. This might have implications for the regional impact.

Figure 2: SRF cavities production steps

Source: Based on information from [Pagani \(2012\)](#), [Singer et al. \(2013\)](#), and input with INFN and DESY staff.

2.4 E. Zanon and Schio

Both companies involved in the SRF cavities production for EXFEL have a long history of working in HEP.

E. Zanon was established in 1919 in Schio in the province of Vicenza (Italy) by Ettore Zanon and initially started as a small workshop that manufactured tanks for the local thriving textile industry. It was only in the 1970s that E. Zanon started its activity in scientific research. E. Zanon entered the HEP business in the 1990s when it produced its first niobium cavities as part of the collaboration with Ansaldo. It then acquired Ansaldo HEP business. In 2020, the HEP branch of E.Zanon was acquired by SIMIC, and a new company, Zanon Research & Innovation, was created. It is now attempting to diversify its business and moving away from relying on HEP.

Research Instruments GmbH was established in 2009 by the core team of ACCEL Instruments GmbH and Interatom, two companies that already operated in the field. These two companies have worked in the SRF cavities production business since 1995.

The insights from our interviews revealed that the two companies differ in size. E. Zanon has only one branch that focuses on High-Energy Physics, located in Schio (Vicenza), in Italy. In 2010, when the contract was assigned, it counted around 30 employees, and another additional 30 employees were hired to fulfil the contract. All the personnel at the company was involved in the contract.

With around 280 employees, Research Instruments is a bigger company than E. Zanon. It has two sites: the corporate headquarters are in Bergisch Gladbach, and the other site is in Dortmund. Unlike E. Zanon, it did not have to recruit additional professional roles as part of the contracts. Looking at the staff involved in the EXFEL project, interviews revealed that only a third of the personnel were engaged in producing the SRF cavities. The company has a more diversified business strategy, and HEP represents only a part of its business.

The fact that E. Zanon has only one site and all its personnel was involved in the contract make it an ideal case to test our approach as it is easier to attribute any potential effect to the procurement contract. In contrast, had we looked at Research Instruments GmbH, we would not have been able to isolate the EXFEL contract's impact from other concurrent ones.

While we are interested in estimating the effects beyond the firm boundaries, suppliers and their characteristics might be playing an important mediating role and affect the magnitude and type of the broader regional impact. Section 3.4 discusses how this can be an issue for the external validity of this study.

As a result of our choice to focus on E. Zanon, this study attempts to estimate the impact of the EXFEL procurement contract on the municipality of Schio, where E. Zanon is located.

Schio is a municipality of around 38 000 inhabitants, located in the province of Vicenza, in the Veneto region (see Figure 3). While our initial assumption is that the effect is concentrated in the municipality of Schio, to account for the location of the E. Zanon plant at the edge of the administrative boundary (see Figure 4) and the possibility that effects go beyond the municipality, we also look at the wider local labour market system as a unit of analysis. This geography is defined by ISTAT (Italian National Statistical Office) using commuting patterns, and it is supposed to capture most of the socio-economic relations in the area. Schio's local labour market system 2011 definition includes other 17 neighbouring

municipalities (see Figure 5). However, as the geographical unit of analysis gets larger, the results might be affected by other confounding factors in other municipalities. Despite these limitations, looking at different geographical levels can shed light on how widely these potential socio-economic benefits spread.

Figure 3: Schio is located in the province of Vicenza, in the north-eastern Italian region of Veneto

Figure 4: E. Zanon (now Zanon Research & Innovation) location (blue pin)

Figure 5: Schio Local labour market system 2011 as defined by ISTAT

Section 3: Approach

This section outlines the approach we use to measure the effects of the EXFEL contract on the economy of Schio, capturing wider impacts beyond the boundaries of the specific supplier. This approach aims to contribute to the existing body of evidence on the effects of HEP procurement that has so far primarily focused on the supplying firms. The idea behind the approach is that the benefits to the supplier and the wider local economy can be integrated into a single framework.

In the rest of this section, firstly, we briefly discuss the conceptual framework and the mechanisms through which we expect these wider benefits to materialize. Secondly, we provide an overview of the Synthetic Control Method (SCM) and of its application for this study. Thirdly, we describe the data we are planning on using for the analysis. Finally, we discuss the issue of external validity and how to address it.

3.1 The conceptual framework

We adopt the "local multiplier framework" recently promoted by Moretti (2010) to conceptualize the possible economic effects of RI procurement contracts on the local economy. This framework was initially developed to measure the impact of the opening of large plants (Greenstone et al., 2015). Therefore, we need to adapt it and extend it to account for the effects of HEP procurement and the specificities of this case study. We do not know a priori how spatially concentrated these effects are. To gain better insights on this, we propose to use different geographical units of analysis in this study. Firstly, we start at the municipality level, and we then extend our research by looking at wider geographical areas such as local labour market systems, as discussed in Section 2.4.

3.11 Tradable and non-tradable sectors

Following Moretti (2010), we divide employment into tradable and non-tradable sectors. The tradable sectors are those that are exposed to competition from outside the region. Typically, the tradable sector consists of the manufacturing industry, but it might also include agriculture, information and communication, financial and insurance activities, electricity & gas, mining & quarrying (OECD, 2018b). The non-tradable category comprises all the sectors that are not exposed to competition from outside the region. This is also referred to as local services and includes construction, hospitality, real estate activities, transport and public administration.

3.12 Direct and indirect effects

We differentiate between direct and indirect effects. According to the public procurement for innovation literature, the contract can guarantee a significant level of production and reduce uncertainty, allowing firms to benefit from economies of scale and technological investment, and ensuring larger profits (Uyarra & Flanagan, 2009). This can lead to an increase in labour demand, and the direct effect is a rise in employment and wages in that industry. The magnitude of these direct effects depends on the size of the contract, the type of product supplied (how labour-intensive it is) and the features of the production process. In the context of HEP procurement, two other factors could amplify the increase in labour demand originating from the contract. One is the subsequent commercialization of products and processes resulting from the company's learning process during the contract duration. The other is reputation: being selected by organizations such as CERN or DESY can signal quality and reliability (Castelnovo et al., 2018). This can attract new contracts from HEP customers – which might lead to a virtuous cycle – and also from commercial ones. These direct effects can be captured by the change after the treatment, in the number of jobs in E. Zanon and all the companies that operate in the same tradable industry.³ The reputation effect can also be measured by the increase in procurement contracts obtained by the supplier and other firms in the supply chain.

³ The NACE Class for Zanon Research & Innovation for 28.99 – Manufacture of other special-purpose machinery n.e.c.. However, this data at such granular level was not available.

The procurement contract might also indirectly impact local employment in the rest of the tradable and non-tradable sectors. Looking at the impact on the rest of the tradable sector, Moretti (2010) argues that this depends on three factors. Firstly, the increase in labour demand might increase labour costs, increase production costs, and lower competitiveness. Firms might shift production to other regions in the long term, negatively impacting local employment. Secondly, the procurement contract might lead to an increase in the demand for intermediate goods and services. The magnitude of this effect depends on how spatially concentrated the supply chain is. Thirdly, the increase in the production in the affected sector may result in more agglomeration. The indirect effects on the tradable sector can be measured by the change in the number of jobs in manufacturing and the rest of the tradable sector.

Looking at the indirect effects on the non-tradable sector, employment in restaurants, retail, and other local services increases because there are more workers in the area or higher wages. In addition, there could be an increase in the number of business visitors to the area due to the original contract. These effects on the non-tradable sector can be measured by the change in the number of jobs in these industries. Moretti (2010) argues that the size of this effect depends on three factors. Firstly, it depends on the type of new jobs in the tradable sector. The evidence suggests that high-skilled jobs have a larger multiplier effect as they pay higher wages, creating a larger demand for local services. Secondly, the effect depends on the consumer preferences for non-tradable and the technology in the non-tradable sectors. More labour-intensive industries might experience a larger increase. Thirdly, the multiplier effect on the non-tradable might also depend on the local labour elasticity. The rise in labour demand and wages in the sector to which the procurement was assigned might crowd out jobs in other industries, potentially leading to a fall in the supply of local services.

The increase in wages and number of jobs may lead to higher demand for housing and, ultimately, house prices unless the supply is infinitely elastic. This rise might also contribute to an increase in labour costs. The effect on housing can be measured by the change in the house prices since the contract was assigned. Beyond demand, it is important to stress that supply issues might also push house prices up. However, it is not possible to disentangle the effects of these two channels. In other words, we will not be able to fully attribute the effect solely to the procurement contract and the subsequent increase in jobs and local demand. It is also important to note that an increase in house prices might have

heterogenous distributional effects. However, accounting for these go beyond the purpose of this study.

3.13 Beyond the local multiplier: innovative capabilities and image-building

Although not included in Moretti's (2010) framework, procurement contracts might also indirectly impact the local innovative capabilities of firms in the tradable sector. The evidence suggests that RI procurement contracts induced R&D spending and innovative capacity (Bastianin et al., 2021; Castelnovo et al., 2018). These R&D efforts could have knowledge spillover effects, which tend to be localized and might impact the local innovative capabilities (Feldman, 1999). The magnitude of these wider effects depends on the absorptive capacities of local actors (Crescenzi & Gagliardi, 2018), on the technological intensity of the product supplied and on the characteristics of the suppliers (Crescenzi et al., 2020). These effects on the local innovative capabilities can be measured by the increase in the number of patents by local firms and local R&D spending.

There might also be other effects that are not necessarily sector-specific. Not all suppliers are located in internationally established clusters, as the case study of Schio showed. Receiving significant contracts from organizations such as CERN or DESY might contribute to the image-building of the area, improving its attractiveness to outside investors and visitors. All sectors might benefit from this branding. For example, an increase in business visitors might lead to a rise in demand for local services such as restaurants and hotels.

3.2 Synthetic control method

This study aims to identify and estimate the additional regional impact of HEP procurement over and above what would have happened in its absence. To establish this causal relationship between the procurement contract and the local economic impact, one needs to compare Schio with a counterfactual. In an ideal scenario, this comparison would involve a "control group", composed of other municipalities with similar characteristics. However, due to the advanced technological requirements and low level of commercialization, only two companies in the world can produce SRF cavities on a large scale today. E. Zanon's location choice might be endogenous. Its presence might also make Schio's industrial profile

different from other municipalities, making it harder to find a control group – other municipalities with similarly specialized firms.

Among the statistical approaches, we considered, the synthetic control method turned out to be the most appropriate to address this challenge. Synthetic control methods have become widely applied in empirical research in social sciences to evaluate a wide range of policies (Abadie, 2020). SCM is based on the idea that when the units of observation are a small number of aggregate entities, a combination of unaffected units often provides a more appropriate comparison than any single unaffected unit alone. In regional studies, this approach is adopted when a "control" location does not exist or cannot be identified. The synthetic control is created by searching for a weighted combination of control units to approximate the unit affected by the treatment in terms of the outcome variable before the treatment. The SCM estimates the effect of the treatment, in our case the procurement contract, by comparing the evolution of the outcome variable of interest for the unit affected by the treatment to the evolution of the same outcome variable for a synthetic control.

In our case, the SCM creates a weighted average of other municipalities that resemble Schio as closely as possible before EXFEL procurement. The group of units used to create this weighted average are known as the "donor pool". To ensure that municipalities in the donor pool are similar to Schio, we include only those in the North of Italy with a population between 10 000 and 100 000. We plan to restrict the sample further to local authorities only located in Veneto in other specifications. In addition, to account for commuting patterns and potential spillover effects in the neighbouring areas, we run the same model for the local labour market systems.

The intuition behind the SCM is that if the trajectory of the outcome variable of interest is similar for both the synthetic and the treated unit before the treatment, any discrepancy we observe post-treatment can be attributed to the policy change. In this study, any difference between Schio and the 'Synthetic' Schio in the post-treatment period can be attributed to the EXFEL procurement contract. A potential issue with this approach is that our donor pool might include municipalities that have received a similar treatment to the one whose effect we are trying to measure (Abadie, 2020). A possible solution to this challenge is excluding municipalities that have received procurement contracts that resemble the EXFEL contract in the post-treatment period.

This method represents a novel approach to the study of RI regional impact. While this is not the first time that SCM has been adopted to estimate the effect of RIs (Helmers & Overman, 2017) or the impact of specific policies on local economies (Nathan, 2020), it has never been used to measure the regional impact of RI procurement contracts. One of the main advantages of this approach is that this type of analysis can be easily replicated for different kinds of contracts, regions and RIs.

3.3 Data

The data we are planning on using for this study will be based on a new dataset stemming from different data sources. Data on the number of employees for the 2004-2018 period comes from the ISTAT Statistical register of active enterprises. This provides data on the number of employees at the municipality level, broken down by ATECO (equivalent to NACE) industry sections. From this dataset, we use the construction, wholesale & retail, transport and hospitality to create the non-tradable sector.⁴ The tradable sector includes agriculture, manufacturing, mining and quarrying, electricity & gas. We then use the ISTAT local labour market 2011 definition to aggregate this at a higher geographical level.

We plan to utilize the data from the CENSUS 2011 on population density, employment rate, population change between 2001 and 2011, the share of young population with a degree, the percentage of workers in high-skilled occupations at the municipality level. Data for this variable refers to 2011, and we use these as covariates when constructing the 'Synthetic' Schio.

To measure the effect on local innovative capabilities, we intend to use patent microdata from the PATSTAT database. This provides detailed information on the location of inventors.

To capture the effect on wages, we use data on taxable income from the Italian Ministry of Economy and Finance.⁵

We use procurement data from the database maintained by the CERN Procurement and Industrial Services group to account for the possibility that other municipalities have received a similar treatment. We are considering including European Economic Area procurement

⁴ This data does not include information on Public administration employees.

⁵ This data is available at the municipality level but it does not have a sectorial breakdown.

data from the Tenders Electronic Daily (TED) database to account for a similar effect and the possible reputation impact on the area.

Finally, we intend to include house prices data from the Italian Tax Office (Agenzia delle Entrate) to account for house price changes.

Table 1: Summary of estimates for the regional study

Effects	Variable	Ex-post estimates
Direct	Change in the number of employees in manufacturing (2010-2018)	Yes
	Change in the number of employees in the manufacture of machinery and employment (2010-2018)	Depending on data availability
Indirect-Induced	Change in the total number of employees (2010-2018)	Yes
	Change in the number of patents (2010-2018)	Yes
	Change in taxable income per capita (2010-2018)	Depending on data availability
	Change in the number of procurement contracts (2010-2018)	Yes
	Change in house prices (2010-2018)	Depending on data availability
	Change in the number of procurement contracts (2010-2018)	Depending on data availability
	Change in the number of employees in the non-tradable sector (2010-2018)	Yes

3.4 External validity

We have chosen to focus on E. Zanon and Schio because we considered this a restricted case in which we could test our novel approach and establish a clearer cause-and-effect relationship (internal validity). A potential problem with the findings arising from this study is external validity: to what extent can the insights from this analysis be generalized to other settings?

Evidence from different strands of the economic literature suggests that other factors could be playing a mediating role. For example, contracts with less specified requirements might leave more room for firms to innovate, generating more knowledge spillovers (Czarnitzki et al., 2020). Firms' characteristics might also influence the magnitude of the local effect. Looking at MNEs, Crescenzi et al. (2020) showed that leading technological firms generate fewer local knowledge spillovers, and similar dynamics might be at play in the RI procurement context. Other local factors external to the firms, such as the quality of local institutions (Ganau & Rodríguez-Pose, 2019) and local human capital (Backman, 2014), might also mediate the regional impact of the procurement contract.

In subsequent studies, to test the external validity of the findings and the approach we propose in this document, it will be insightful to look at other procurement contracts involving different technologies, firms, and regions. However, the possibility of applying this approach to other cases depends on data availability, and it might require additional resources.

Section 5: Conclusions

This report outlined the criteria for the case study selection. It proposed a novel approach to identify and estimate the regional effects that a particle-collider-based research infrastructure set up as a worldwide distributed project can generate.

This document identified SRF cavities as the most relevant technology for this study based on carefully defined selection criteria. Using the insights from our scoping study that comprised interviews with SRF cavities experts, this report proposes to focus on the EXFEL project, the largest deployment of SRF cavities to date and the first time this technology was produced in industry. After examining the SRF cavities procurement and production process for EXFEL, this document identified the municipality of Schio, where E. Zanon, one of the two suppliers, is located as the unit of analysis. The company's features and the production process suggested that this is a better defined and contained case to test the novel approach presented in this document and attribute the potential effects on the local economy to the contract.

This document also presented the local multiplier framework through which the effects of HEP procurement can be conceptualized and identified. To estimate these effects, this report identified the synthetic control method as the most appropriate counterfactual technique for this analysis. This will be the first time that state-of-the-art counterfactual methods are used to estimate the local socio-economic impact of RIs, making an important contribution to the growing body of evidence on this area.

By focusing on one case study, the issue of external validity may arise: to what extent the findings of the analysis can be generalized to other settings (technologies, regions, RIs, contracts)? Several factors such as firm characteristics and external local conditions might be playing a mediating role and ultimately affect the local economic impact. The advantage of the proposed approach is that it can be applied to different settings, conditional on the demand for this type of analysis, data availability and resources.

The next step in this research project is to produce a report summarising and interpreting the quantitative estimates for the case study we identified in this document (LSE-RD 1.4). The deadline for this deliverable is June 2022.

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Appendix

Table 2: List of interviewees

Interviewee	Organization
Walter Venturini Delsonaro	CERN
Ed Daly	Jefferson Lab
John Rathke	AES
Ted Roark	Roarkfab
Michael Neumann	Formerly at DESY
Riko Wichmann	DESY
Hans Weise	DESY
Paolo Michelato	INFN Milano
Daniele Sertore	INFN Milano
Ambra Gresele	Zanon Research & Innovation
Michael Pekeler	Research Instruments GmbH
Marco Roveta	Criotec
Hendrie Derking	Cryoworld